

In a recent test series (2002-03), various commercially-available foot protection systems were tested with cadaveric specimens, with charges of 75g C4 explosive. For the cadaver tests, radiographs were taken after the detonation, and inspected by a team of surgeons. Figure 8 shows examples of post-blast radiographs corresponding to a conventional blast boot (a) and the Spider Boot (b), for the detonation of a 75g C4 explosive charge. It was found that while the bones were severely crushed for the conventional boot case, the integrity of the bones was preserved for the Spider Boot case. One of the key findings from these tests was that only the Spider Boot could consistently provide sufficient protection against explosive charges equal to, or in excess of, 75g C4* .